

Integrated germplasm improvement – upland

Two improved upland rice varieties for Bangladesh

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BRRI recently released improved upland rice varieties BR20 and BR21 for direct seeded aus season in high-rainfall areas of Bangladesh. BR20 (BR201-193-1) was derived from IR272-4-1-2-J1/IR5; BR21 (BR1656-22-1) came from C22/IET1444. Both varieties have intermediate plant height, short duration, and high yield potential and are moderately resistant to lodging and drought. Both are moderately resistant to bacterial blight, bacterial leaf streak, rice tungro virus,

brown spot, and grain discoloration.

BR20 averages 133 filled grains/panicle, with 1,000-grain weight of 21 g. BR21 has 112 filled grains/panicle with 1,000-grain weight of 23 g.

The new varieties yielded at least

two times more than existing local upland varieties (Table 1). Physicochemical and cooking qualities of BR20 and BR21 are compared with local popular upland variety Hashikalmi in Table 2. □

Table 1. Average grain yield and some agronomic traits of BR20 and BR21 in direct seeded upland conditions in Bangladesh, 1985-88.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Average grain yield ^a (t/ha)						Increase over local check variety (%)
			On station 1985 (10)	On farm 1986 (23)	Demonstration in farmers' field			Mean	
					1986 (12)	1987 (6)	1988 (70)		
BR20	105-112	110-120	3.8	2.4	3.1	3.2	3.08	3.11	107
BR21	95-105	95-110	3.1	2.5	3.1	3.2	3.06	3.01	101
Local upland variety (check)	90-100	110-115	1.3	1.2	-	1.6	1.85	1.50	-

^aNumbers in parentheses are number of test sites.

Table 2. Physicochemical and cooking qualities of BR20 and BR21.

Variety	Milling outturn (%)	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L/B ratio	Protein (%)	Amylose (%)	Gelatinization temp	Imbibition ratio	Elongation ratio	Size and shape	Endosperm	Tenderness
BR20	73	5.1	2.2	2.3	7.8	26	6.0	4.0	1.5	Medium bold	Translucent	Medium hard
BR21	73	5.2	2.0	2.6	8.3	26	4.5	4.0	1.5	Medium bold	Translucent	Medium hard
Hashikalmi (local check)	72	4.8	2.1	2.3	7.0	29	4.0	3.8	1.4	Short bold	White belly	Hard

Integrated germplasm improvement – deepwater

NDGR402, a promising new floating rice

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NDGR402, a pure line selection from local variety Goanth, can withstand gradual increases in water depth up to 2.0-2.5 m. Its grains are short and bold with red kernels, L/B ratio of 2.1, and 1,000-grain weight of 30.9 g. It takes 215 d from seeding to maturity.

It was selected from 13 entries including local selections and promis-

ing lines from cross RP31-49-2/LMN and check variety Jalmagna evaluated for three consecutive seasons 1985-87. Test plots were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Seeds were directly sown in Apr in 5- × 2-m plots. Fertilizer was applied 30-30 kg NP/ha as basal and 30 kg N/ha in two equal splits before flooding and at tillering.

NDGR402 (IET10235) gave the highest yield, an average 4.9 t/ha--17% more than check Jalmagna. Plant height ranged from 220 to 311 cm, depending on peak water depth. It showed drought tolerance similar to

Jalmagna (and better than Jaladhi 1) at the vegetative stage and good elongation and kneeing ability at later stages.

Its higher yield potential may be ascribed mainly to number of grains/panicle and more productive tillers (Table 1).

NDGR402 looked promising in All India Rice Improvement Trials at Ghagharaghat, Chinsurah, North Lakhimpur, and Pusa during 1987 wet season and in the Uniform Varietal Trial in 1988. It yielded 4.3 t/ha in 1987 and 2.3 t/ha in 1988 wet season at Ghagharaghat and was superior to checks in 1988 at North Lakhimpur

Table 1. Grain yield and agronomic traits of promising deepwater entries. Ghagharaghat, U.P., India, 1985-87.

Variety or line	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)			Av of 3 yr				
		1985	1986	1987	Yield (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)
NDGR401	Pureline selection	4.5	3.0	4.3	3.9	187	285	23	156
NDGR402	Selection from Goanth	5.0	4.5	5.1	4.9	188	275	24	164
NDGR403	Selection from Kalaungi	4.4	3.4	4.5	4.1	184	267	26	153
NDGR404	Selection from Sainger	4.5	3.7	4.5	4.2	188	280	24	140
FRRS43-3		3.0	0.9	3.3	2.4	181	304	21	160
TCA258		3.7	3.0	4.4	3.7	190	272	24	134
NDGR411	RP31-49-2/LMN920312	3.4	2.4	3.8	3.2	193	273	22	129
NDGR412	RP31-49-2/LMN920312-1	3.1	0.5	4.6	2.7	184	255	27	127
NDGR413	RP31-49-2/LMN920316-1	3.0	2.1	4.1	3.0	188	264	27	149
NDGR414	RP31-49-2/LMN920316-2	3.7	2.8	3.4	3.3	186	255	27	151
NDGR416	RP31-49-2/LMN920351	4.1	3.1	3.7	3.6	189	263	26	136
NDGR419	RP31-49-2/LMN1045-3	2.5	1.6	3.8	2.6	192	256	23	143
Jalmagna	(local check)	4.3	4.2	4.2	4.2	194	323	24	145
LSD (0.05)		0.9	0.4	1.0					
CV (%)		18.3	19.6	30.3					
Max water depth (m)		2.7	1.8	2.4					

Table 2. Performance of NDGR402 at 4 locations in uniform varietal trials. Ghagharaghat, U.P., India, 1985-87.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Panicles (no./m ²)	Drought score
	Ghagharaghat		Chinsurah, 1987	North Lakhimpur, 1988	Pusa, 1988		
	1987	1988					
NDGR402 (IET10235)	4.3	2.3	0.4	3.2	1.8	132	5
Jaladhi 1 (national check)	1.2	1.6	0.3	2.6	1.0	89	9
Jalmagna (local check)	2.7	2.4	0.2	2.6	1.2	89	5
LSD (0.05)	0.9	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.4		
CV (%) 20.3	23.5		45.6	10.1	31.4		
Water depth (m)	1.16	2.45	0.95	1.03	1.80		

and Pusa (Table 2). It survived four consecutive flashfloods at North Lakhimpur.

NDGR402 has been recommended

for on-farm testing under deepwater conditions in Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and Assam. □

Seed technology

Application of immuno-radiometric assay (IRMA) in rice seed inspection for *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*

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A rapid IRMA for identifying *X. c. pv. oryzicola* in rice seeds was established by nonspecific combination of ¹²⁵I-protein A with serum immunoglobulin (IgG) obtained from domestic rabbits in Hainan Province.

The rabbits were immunized with isolates of *X. c. pv. oryzicola* (Ag) by the intravenous injection method and the specific antiserum against the Ag obtained after 2 mo. The specific

antibody (Ab) in the antiserum reacted with the Ag of samples (about 0.2-2.0 g for each sample) in the soaking solution (0.1 M, pH 6.0 phosphate buffer solution containing 0.5% bovine serum albumin and 0.05% Tween 20) to produce the Ag-Ab complex.

The complex reacted on the protein A, which had been labeled by ¹²⁵I, to form a radioactive complex with the labeled protein A. Finally, the radioactive complex was tested on the gamma counter for its radioactivity (counts per minute, cpm). If the cpm ratio of a tested sample and disease-free check was equal to or more than 1.50, the sample was considered positive, or diseased.

The results showed that IRMA was not only more sensitive but more specific for *X. c. pv. oryzicola* in rice seed. At a concentration of 500 bacterial cells/ml, the intrabatch and interbatch coefficients of variation were about 11.2 and 14.2%, respectively. The antiserum showed weak cross-reaction only against *X. c. pv. oryzae*, 4.7%; *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *mori*, 4.3%; *X. c. pv. malvacearum*, 2.4%; and the other miscellaneous serums of rice, 0.4%. The cpm ratios of the bacteria ranged from 1.08 to 1.37.

We tested 331 seed samples from seven provinces by IRMA and the concentration inoculation method (CI). The CI method involves inoculating rice seedlings by the needle pricking method during tillering. The

Detection of *X.c. pv. oryzicola* of rice seeds from diseased areas by IRMA and CI methods. Hainan Province, China, 1989.

Place of origin	Varieties examined (no.)	Varieties (no.) with positive reaction	
		IRMA	CI
Hainan	5	5	4
Guangxi	3	2	1
Guangdong	4	3	2
Hunan	7	5	3
Jiangxi	19	11	6
Zhejiang	282 ^a	249	168
Jiang	11 ^b	9	6
Total	331	284	190

^a The majority were obtained from artificially inoculated plants. ^b All were from artificially inoculated plants.